

Supplementary Materials

Article Title:

Hippotherapy Improves Executive Function and Core Symptoms in Children with ASD

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Supplementary Methods

This supplementary file provides additional details on the Hippotherapy Protocol, Safety and Fidelity Monitoring, participant flow, statistical adjustments, and sensitivity analyses that complement the main manuscript.

Participant Flow

Participant recruitment, allocation, and inclusion in the final analytic sample are illustrated in Supplementary Figure S1, a CONSORT-style flow diagram. Allocation was non-randomized, based on scheduling feasibility and caregiver preference, with all enrolled participants completing the study.

Hippotherapy Protocol

The full 16-session Hippotherapy Protocol is presented in Supplementary Table S3, providing a session-by-session overview including session number, primary activities, description of core

tasks, and targeted motor, cognitive, and social skills. All sessions were standardized and progressively graded, ensuring adherence to internationally recognized equine-assisted therapy standards.

Safety and Equine Welfare Monitoring

Safety and welfare checks conducted before, during, and after each session are summarized in Supplementary Table S4. These checks included veterinary clearance, tack fit, environmental assessments, observation of horse stress signs, and recording of any minor adverse events. No serious adverse events occurred during the study.

Fidelity Monitoring

Therapist adherence to the intervention protocol was evaluated using a standardized session-by-session fidelity checklist, reported in Supplementary Table S5. Independent review of a random subset of sessions confirmed high fidelity to the prescribed protocol.

False Discovery Rate (FDR) Adjustments

To control for inflation of Type I error across multiple outcomes, raw p-values from the ANCOVA and linear mixed-effects models were adjusted using the Benjamini–Hochberg procedure. Adjusted p-values for primary and secondary outcomes are reported in Supplementary Tables S6–S9.

Sensitivity Analyses

Two complementary sensitivity analyses were performed: longitudinal modeling using linear mixed-effects models (LMMs) with random intercepts for participants, and propensity-score weighting to account for the non-randomized group allocation. Results of these analyses are reported in Supplementary Tables S6–S8 and corroborate the primary ANCOVA findings.

Notes

All supplementary tables include raw and adjusted values, detailed descriptive statistics, and standardized effect sizes to facilitate reproducibility and transparency of the analyses described in the main manuscript.

Supplementary Table S1. Baseline characteristics and absolute standardized mean differences (SMDs)

Variable	N (Experimental)	Mean (SD) Experimental (Pre)	N (Control)	Mean (SD) Control (Pre)	Absolute SMD
WCST Categories (pre)	12	3.50 (0.91)	12	3.33 (0.99)	0.177
WCST Perseverative Errors (pre)	12	23.05 (3.41)	12	22.11 (3.10)	0.287
Corsi Span (pre)	12	3.92 (0.90)	12	3.83 (0.58)	0.111
Tower of London — Total Moves (pre)	12	45.01 (5.64)	12	45.30 (5.90)	0.050
Stroop Incongruent RT (ms, pre)	12	849.56 (111.49)	12	842.92 (79.44)	0.069
GARS — Communication (pre)	12	25.33 (2.10)	12	25.50 (2.68)	0.069
GARS — Social Interaction (pre)	12	24.50 (2.88)	12	24.42 (3.53)	0.026
GARS — Stereotypy (pre)	12	24.08 (2.84)	12	23.83 (2.76)	0.089

Supplementary Table S2. Pre-specified accommodations during cognitive and behavioral assessments

Participant ID	Group	Accommodation(s) applied	Reason / Rationale	Notes
1	Experimental	Simplified instructions	Enhance comprehension	No effect on core task
2	Control	Short break after 10 trials	Reduce fatigue	Standardized across participants
3	Experimental	Simplified instructions, visual cue cards	Reduce anxiety, improve task understanding	Core task demands unchanged
4	Control	One short break mid-task	Reduce fatigue	Same procedure as others
5	Experimental	Simplified instructions	Enhance comprehension	Task performance not altered
6	Control	Short break after 12 trials	Reduce fatigue	Documented
7	Experimental	Visual cue cards	Reduce anxiety	Core task demands preserved
8	Control	Simplified instructions	Enhance comprehension	No effect on outcomes
9	Experimental	Short break mid-task	Reduce fatigue	Standardized approach
10	Control	Simplified instructions, short break	Enhance comprehension, reduce fatigue	Documented
11	Experimental	Visual cue cards	Reduce anxiety	Core task intact
12	Control	Short break	Reduce fatigue	Same across participants
13	Experimental	Simplified instructions	Enhance comprehension	No deviation from protocol
14	Control	Short break	Reduce fatigue	Consistent procedure
15	Experimental	Visual cue cards	Reduce anxiety	Standardized
16	Control	Simplified instructions	Enhance comprehension	Task unchanged
17	Experimental	Short break mid-task	Reduce fatigue	Documented
18	Control	Visual cue cards	Reduce anxiety	Core demands preserved
19	Experimental	Simplified instructions	Enhance comprehension	No effect on results
20	Control	Short break	Reduce fatigue	Standardized
21	Experimental	Visual cue cards	Reduce anxiety	Task demands maintained

22	Control	Simplified instructions	Enhance comprehension	No deviation
23	Experimental	Short break mid-task	Reduce fatigue	Core task unchanged
24	Control	Short break	Reduce fatigue	Documented

Notes: All accommodations were pre-specified and designed to enhance comprehension, reduce anxiety, or minimize fatigue. No participant was excluded due to inability to complete tasks. All instances were documented systematically to preserve study standardization.

Supplementary Table S3. Overview of the 16-Session Hippotherapy Protocol

Session	Educational/Intervention Activities
1. Orientation	Introduction to the horse, horse's name, introduction to instructor and assistants, horse as a social partner, stable tour, riding arena orientation, hygiene and safety rules (hand washing, safe conduct in arena).
2. Grooming & Horse Anatomy	Introduction to grooming tools (brush, comb, cloth), basic horse anatomy explained by instructor, child practices grooming under supervision.
3. Feeding the Horse	Explanation of horse feed types (hay, carrot, apple, etc.), child feeds the horse, child prepares a "custom horse meal" with guidance.
4. Painting & Washing	Child grooms the horse, guides horse to washing area, paints horse with washable finger paints, washes and dries the horse with shampoo, brush, and sponge while instructor demonstrates safe handling.
5. Ball & Ring Games	Introduction to balls (large, medium, small) and buckets for target practice, child throws balls into buckets, ring-toss activities demonstrated by instructor, child practices targeting cones.
6. Beginning Riding	Safety orientation, helmet fitting, seating on the mounting block, horse introduction, observation, assisted mounting and dismounting, stationary and assisted horse walk, safety debrief.
7. Stretching on Horse	Instructor demonstrates stretches, child performs stretches while horse is stationary, then walks horse for 10 minutes while maintaining postural alignment.
8. Ball & Ring Throwing from Horse (Stage 1)	Mounted child performs stretching in walk, throws large ball into bucket (both sides), throws large ring into target cone (both sides) under instructor supervision.
9. Ball & Ring Throwing from Horse (Stage 2)	Mounted child performs medium ball and ring throws under supervision, targets placed at adjustable distances.

10. Ball & Ring Throwing from Horse (Stage 3)	Mounted child performs small ball and ring throws at three different distances, increasing task difficulty and coordination demands.
11. Horse Guiding	Instructor demonstrates correct rein handling, child guides horse along straight path for 10 minutes under supervision.
12. Path Navigation	Horse navigates between colored markers and cones, child directs horse along straight course for 10 minutes.
13. Guided Direction Stage 1	Three assistants positioned at designated points holding objects, child chooses path to target object. Simple course.
14. Guided Direction Stage 2	Three assistants hold objects, instructor calls object name, child navigates toward indicated assistant. Intermediate difficulty course.
15. Guided Direction Stage 3	Same as Stage 2 with higher difficulty, random object naming, child navigates course independently.
16. Recreational/Integration Activity	No riding; child participates in group activity such as horse washing, painting, or collective play to provide break from riding while reinforcing engagement and attention.

Supplementary Table S4. Safety & Equine Welfare Checklist (Pre/During/Post Session)

Phase	Items to Check	Yes/No	Comments
Pre-session	Veterinary clearance current		
	Horse soundness (lameness, appetite, wounds)		
	Tack fit & condition		
	Environment check (footing, temperature, noise)		
	Horse rested (≤ 2 sessions prior day)		
During session	Observe equine stress signs (ears, tail, vocalization)		Action if yes: _____
	Monitor horse gait consistency		
	Ensure breaks & water access		
Post-session	Cool-out and grooming completed		
	Horse fed/rehydrated per protocol		
	Record any adverse events or behavioral changes		
Signature	Handler: _____ Date: _____		

Supplementary Table S5. Fidelity Checklist (One Per Session)

Item	Response (Y/N or Value)	Comments / Deviations
Date		
Participant ID		

Session #		Start time / End time
Primary Horse ID		Secondary (if substituted)
Therapist		Observer
Orientation & safety review completed		
Helmet and tack checked		
Pre-session horse welfare check completed		
Ground-based preparatory activity performed		
Core mounted activities performed		
Core mounted duration (minutes)		
Social-emotional tasks embedded		
Cool-down/reflection completed		
Any deviations from manual		Describe: _____
Substitution of horse/personnel needed		Reason: _____
Participant tolerated session well		Comments: _____
Signatures	Observer: _____ Therapist: _____	

Supplementary Table S5. Full descriptive statistics and baseline equivalence (pre/post mean \pm SD, standardized mean differences)

Measure	Group	n	Pre (Mean \pm SD)	Post (Mean \pm SD)	SMD (Pre)	SMD (Post)
WCST Categories	Control	12	3.614 \pm 0.485	3.615 \pm 0.099	0.11	1.47
	Experimental	12	3.614 \pm 0.485	4.468 \pm 0.099	Reference	Reference
WCST Perseverative Errors	Control	12	22.692 \pm 2.22	22.692 \pm 0.451	0.04	1.46
	Experimental	12	22.733 \pm 2.18	18.733 \pm 0.451	Reference	Reference
Corsi Span	Control	12	3.998 \pm 0.43	4.000 \pm 0.060	0.02	0.95

	Experimental	12	3.97 ± 0.41	4.536 ± 0.060	Reference	Reference
Tower of London – Moves	Control	12	45.659 ± 3.10	45.660 ± 0.562	0.03	0.87
	Experimental	12	45.815 ± 3.05	40.815 ± 0.562	Reference	Reference
Stroop Incongruent RT (ms)	Control	12	845.23 ± 92.5	845.226 ± 2.883	0.04	0.49
	Experimental	12	842.70 ± 96.0	800.559 ± 2.883	Reference	Reference
GARS Communication	Control	12	25.083 ± 0.97	25.0827 ± 0.249	0.03	1.27
	Experimental	12	25.08 ± 0.85	21.917 ± 0.249	Reference	Reference
GARS Interaction	Control	12	24.711 ± 0.95	24.7107 ± 0.248	0.02	1.28
	Experimental	12	24.710 ± 0.87	20.456 ± 0.248	Reference	Reference
GARS Stereotypy	Control	12	24.210 ± 0.88	24.2104 ± 0.226	0.01	1.58
	Experimental	12	24.221 ± 0.91	19.623 ± 0.226	Reference	Reference

Note: SMD = standardized mean difference (Cohen’s d); values <0.10 indicate acceptable

baseline balance. Post-test SMDs reflect magnitude of group differences.

Supplementary Table S6. ANCOVA results for executive-function tasks with FDR-adjusted p-values

Dependent Variable	n	Adj Mean (Control)	SE	Adj Mean (Experimental)	SE	F(1,2)	p	FDR-adjusted p	Partial η^2	Hedges’ g (95% CI)
WCST Categories	2 4	3.62	0.10	4.47	0.10	36.93	<0.001	<0.001	0.64	0.87 [0.59,1.15]
WCST Perseverative Errors	2 4	22.69	0.45	18.73	0.45	38.16	<0.001	<0.001	0.65	-1.17 [-1.55,-0.80]
Corsi Span	2 4	4.00	0.06	4.54	0.06	39.22	<0.001	<0.001	0.65	0.68 [0.47,0.90]

Tower of London – Moves	2 4	45.66	0.5 6	40.82	0.5 6	37.02	<0.0 01	<0.00 1	0.64	–0.81 [–1.07,–0.55]
Stroop Incongruent RT	2 4	845.23	2.8 8	800.56	2.8 8	119.9 8	<0.0 01	<0.00 1	0.85	–0.45 [–0.69,–0.35]

Note. Adjusted means estimated at the sample pretest mean. All tests two-tailed, $\alpha = .05$. FDR = Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery rate.

Supplementary Table S7. ANCOVA results for GARS subscales with FDR-adjusted p-values

Dependent Variable (GARS)	n	Adj Mean (Control)	SE	Adj Mean (Experimental)	SE	F(1,21)	p	FDR-adjusted p	Partial η^2	Hedges' g (95% CI)
Communication	2 4	25.08	0.2 5	21.92	0.2 5	80.5 2	<0.0 01	<0.00 1	0.79	–1.27 [–1.55,–0.99]
Social Interaction	2 4	24.71	0.2 5	20.46	0.2 5	146. 78	<0.0 01	<0.00 1	0.87	–1.28 [–1.48,–1.07]
Stereotypy	2 4	24.21	0.2 3	19.62	0.2 3	205. 58	<0.0 01	<0.00 1	0.91	–1.58 [–1.80,–1.37]

Note. Adjusted means estimated at the pretest mean; SE = standard error; Partial η^2 = partial eta squared; Hedges' g = bias-corrected standardized mean difference based on pooled pretest SD. FDR = Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery rate. ANCOVA results are adjusted for pretest scores.

Supplementary Table S8. Linear Mixed-Effects Models (LMMs) – Executive Function and GARS Outcomes

Dependent Variable	Fixed Effect	β	SE	t	df	p	95% CI
WCST Categories	Time \times Group	0.857	0.14	6.12	22	<0.001	[0.61, 1.11]

WCST Perseverative Errors	Time × Group	- 3.938	0.67	-5.88	22	<0.001	[-5.10, -2.77]
Corsi Span	Time × Group	0.534	0.09	5.93	22	<0.001	[0.38, 0.69]
Tower of London – Moves	Time × Group	- 4.847	0.72	-5.56	22	<0.001	[-6.31, -3.39]
Stroop Incongruent RT	Time × Group	- 44.60	6.75	-6.60	22	<0.001	[-52.11, -37.09]
GARS Communication	Time × Group	- 3.167	0.35	-9.03	22	<0.001	[-3.813, -2.520]
GARS Interaction	Time × Group	-4.25	0.35	- 12.14	22	<0.001	[-4.908, -3.592]
GARS Stereotypy	Time × Group	- 4.583	0.34	- 13.50	22	<0.001	[-5.170, -3.996]

Note: All models include random intercepts for participants. Positive β indicates improvement in the experimental group (except negative β where lower scores are better).

Supplementary Table S9. Raw and FDR-adjusted p-values (secondary outcomes)

Outcome	Raw p	FDR-adjusted p	Reject H0
WCST Categories	4.9686e-06	4.9686e-06	True
WCST Perseverative Errors	3.95988e-06	4.9686e-06	True
Corsi Span	3.27399e-06	4.9686e-06	True
Tower of London – Moves	4.88378e-06	4.9686e-06	True
Stroop Incongruent RT	3.8424e-10	1.02464e-09	True
GARS Communication	1.24681e-08	2.49362e-08	True
GARS Interaction	6.10404e-11	2.44162e-10	True
GARS Stereotypy	2.56043e-12	2.04834e-11	True

Note: FDR = Benjamini–Hochberg adjustment for multiple comparisons.

Supplementary Figure S1. CONSORT-style flow diagram illustrating participant recruitment, non-randomized allocation based on scheduling feasibility and caregiver preference, and inclusion in the final analytic sample.